

A Novel Tactile Device for Safe Human-Robot Interaction in Industrial Scenarios

Francesco Grella¹, Giulia Baldini¹, Roberto Canale¹, Si Ao Wang¹, Alessandro Albini³, Michal Jilich², Giorgio Cannata¹, Matteo Zoppi²

Abstract—In this paper we present a novel device based on tactile sensing, designed to enable physical interaction between an industrial robot and its operator. Capacitive tactile sensing technology has been embodied in a cylinder-shaped handle, in order to exploit physical interaction information to safely enable human-robot cooperative tasks. The device provides interaction force by measuring exerted pressure, as well as a semantic detection of the human hand. We use the latter feature in order to detect voluntary human-robot interaction, identified when the user is firmly grasping the device with one hand. A prototype has been implemented using 3D printing technology its operation assessment has been performed with bench tests.

Index Terms—Tactile Sensing, Human-Robot Interaction, Deep Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

When considering the context of *Industry 4.0*, flexible robotic technologies are fundamental since robots are required to be way more than assembly chain elements with predefined tasks. Manipulators are expected to exhibit more flexible behaviors with respect to their environment in order to adapt and properly tune their behavior during task execution. [1], [2]. Human operators become in fact a fundamental part of robot's operating environment, since they represent external unpredictable agents to comply with. This concept indeed yields considerations about social and safety issues, well addressed in occupational safety literature like [3], proving the fact that new technologies are required to implement and promote safe and proficient human-robot interaction. In this work we address the design of a sensing device to be used as physical interface between a human operator and a robotic manipulator. The output of tactile sensors covering the device are used to detect when a user is *voluntarily interacting* with it. The key-idea is to use hand detection to recognize voluntary interaction, which we define as a situation in which the operator is firmly grasping the handle. The device and an example of output from the tactile sensors is showed in Figure 1. The device has been designed to fit the use-case scenario considered in the *CoLLaboratE* H2020 project [4], consisting of a windshield assembly task. In this context, a human operator has to interact with the device placed on the robot gripper, enabling a collaborative phase of the task, where the robot serves as a 6DOF movable support tool by means

Fig. 1: Proposed device for the collaborative task. The drawing resumes the three main components of the handle. On the left an example of tactile sensors output which is used for the training the classifier proposed in [5] is shown.

of admittance control, achieved with a force/torque sensor mounted on the flange.

II. FIELD SETUP

The use-case in which the proposed device will be validated consists of a collaborative human-robot assembly cell.

In particular the worker and the manipulator will cooperate to perform windshield assembly and maintenance operations, in particular the human will be using four identical tactile handles as interface with the robot. The devices are mounted on the frame of a vacuum gripper built for the task (Fig.2), on four carbon tubes which act as support. Even if the described artificial skin allows computation of exerted force through pressure measurements, this feature falls beyond the purpose

Fig. 2: Simplified view of the windshield assembly gripper. Tactile sensing devices, corresponding to handles are mounted in a configuration that allows manipulation both frontally and by the corners.

¹DIBRIS, University of Genova, Italy.

²DIME, University of Genova, Italy.

³Oxford Robotics Institute, Oxford, United Kingdom

Corresponding author's email: francesco.grella@edu.unige.it

Fig. 3: The handle is 3D printed with PLA material. Tactile sensors (green circles in the images) are integrated on the handle shell. (a) Upper side of the main body; (b) left cap.

of this specific application. The admittance control of the gripper's pose is enabled through a 6DOF force/torque sensor placed right below the windshield support. The distributed sensing capabilities of the handles are exploited as a safety measure in order to enable robot's collaborative operation mode, a *zero-gravity* compliant cartesian controller.

III. DEVICE DESIGN

The device is a cylinder-shaped handle intended to be wrapped around a cylindrical bar, meant to be installed on ad-hoc supports or as part of a frame. Our design choices are motivated by the following assumptions:

- The cylindrical shape of the handle has been chosen since it's simple and easy to grasp: in fact it ensures a natural grasping pose for the human hand.
- The external diameter of the handle is 64mm and is the result of a trade-off: this size is larger with respect to the optimal diameter expected for a cylindrical tool [6] but allows an easier placement of flexible sensors and internal cables, anyway ensuring a firm grasp for the user.
- The division in two halves makes the cabling and the maintenance easier, and allows quick assembly around the supporting frame, which also has to be cylindrical. The two halves are kept together by using neodymium magnets and steel pins.

The handle is covered with the CySkin [7] sensor, measuring the contact pressure by capacitance variation induced by deformation of the ground plane. Each half of the handle has 300 discrete sensing elements (*i.e. taxels*) arranged in 30 flexible triangular modules, which ensure an exhaustive coverage of the cylindrical surface. In order to reduce as much as possible the blind spots sensors have been added also to the side faces of the handle: one peg-shaped cap for each side has been covered with two modules (*20 taxels*), for a total of 640. One half and a cap are shown in Fig.3. The complete handle is shown in Fig.1. Conductive lycra is used as ground plane: it's wrapped separately over the two halves and fixed by Velcro strips placed in the internal space; two small patches also cover the sensors on the caps and fixed by two masks.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

Hand recognition is performed through *HandsNet*, a convolutional neural network presented in [5] which acts as

binary classifier on the flattened tactile image detected by the sensors. We have performed tests to verify the operation of the device on a static setup, depicted in Fig.1. The test bench configuration consists of a fixed base on which the handle is mounted by using two external attachments, used to lodge the terminal parts of the two caps. In this case the internal bar is made by two 3D printed cylindrical segments, in order to provide a support for the caps and the handle.

To have a better generalization of the model on data acquired by the handle, we have performed fine-tuning of the convolutional neural network (CNN) presented in [5] using a new dataset, collected from 18 subjects while grasping the handle. The dataset has been split by following a 70%/10%/20% partition for train/validation/test sets respectively. A 10% set for cross-validation has been chosen due to the low number of hyperparameters to tune. The train set was then used to fine-tune the CNN for 80 epochs using the Stochastic Gradient Descent [8], a batch size of 64 and a fixed learning rate of 0.005. The fine training procedure led to an accuracy of 98.08% and 94.83% on the validation and test sets respectively.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this article we have presented the prototype of a device for Physical Human-Robot Interaction designed to be modular and robot-independent. We have shown how the device can be used to detect voluntary human-robot interaction, identified in a grasping action and modeled as an object detection problem. The previously trained *HandsNet* has been fine-tuned with a new dataset acquired from the handle, showing good detection accuracy. We are currently working on the integration of four identical handles on the gripper shown in Fig.2. We are also exploring methods to exploit the resulting force applied on the handle in order to directly control the robot.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Parodi and G. G. Gerio, "Aura: An example of collaborative robot for automotive and general industry applications," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 11, pp. 338–345, 2017, 27th International Conference on Flexible Automation and Intelligent Manufacturing, FAIM2017, 27-30 June 2017, Modena, Italy. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2351978917303207>
- [2] F. Sherwani, M. M. Asad, and B. S. K. K. Ibrahim, "Collaborative robots and industrial revolution 4.0 (ir 4.0)," in *2020 International Conference on Emerging Trends in Smart Technologies (ICETST)*, 2020, pp. 1–5.
- [3] S. Bragança, E. Costa, I. Castellucci, and P. M. Arezes, *A Brief Overview of the Use of Collaborative Robots in Industry 4.0: Human Role and Safety*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 641–650. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-14730-3-68>
- [4] "Collaborate project," <https://collaborate-project.eu/>.
- [5] A. Albini and G. Cannata, "Pressure distribution classification and segmentation of human hands in contact with the robot body," *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 668–687, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0278364920907688>
- [6] Y.-K. Kong and B. Lowe, "Optimal cylindrical handle diameter for grip force tasks," *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, vol. 35, pp. 495–507, 06 2005.
- [7] M. Maggiali, G. Cannata, P. Maiolino, G. Metta, M. Randazzo, and G. Sandini, "Embedded distributed capacitive tactile sensor," *Mechatronics*, 07 2008.
- [8] H. Robbins and S. Monro, "A Stochastic Approximation Method," *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 400 – 407, 1951. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1214/aoms/1177729586>